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IMAGINATION AS A MENTAL PROCESS AND FORMS OF ITS MANIFESTATIONS

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***Annotatsiya:** the author of the article addressed a very interesting mental process. Almost all human culture - material, spiritual - is the fruit, the product of people's imagination and creativity. The process of imagination enables a person to go beyond the real world.*

***Key words:** involuntary, voluntary, recreating, creative, dream, fantasy, dreams, creativity.*

Introduction

The article examines scientific and practical views on the nature of human imagination, various approaches to understanding the essence of imagination, its features. Imagination is a mental process of creating new images by bringing a person's existing knowledge into a new combination and the basis of visual imaginative thinking. Imagination is based on a person's previous experience. In order to begin to fantasize, a person must see, hear, receive impressions and keep them in memory. The necessary knowledge is not always available to solve everyday problems. In imagination and fantasy, a person goes beyond the real world in time and space.

Hypotheses explaining imagination:

- * The hypothesis of random discoveries. According to it, all discoveries were made
- * The hypothesis of recombination. Imagination is aimed at shuffling, reinstalling sensations, ideas, principles, rules by trial and error.

Imagination is conditioned by the activity of the brain. The formation of new images from ideas available in memory is the physiological basis of imagination. Imagination affects a person's well-being. Thus, a picture of danger created by the imagination causes an increase in heart rate, a change in breathing. There are known facts of suggestion of signs of some diseases (medical students in their junior years find many diseases in themselves, although in reality they do not exist).

If a person imagines the movement of some part of his own body (arms, legs, torso tilt, head rotation, etc.), but does not perform this movement, then in the muscles that should perform it, impulses are recorded similar to those that are registered during the actual execution of the movement. These are

the so-called ideomotor acts.

In clinical practice, cases of morbid changes in imagination are not uncommon. The most indicative is a hallucination, in which the patient "perceives" a non-existent object. According to the degree of arbitrariness, a distinction is made between voluntary (aimed at solving some problem in wakefulness) and involuntary imagination (sleep);

Voluntary imagination manifests itself in cases when new images or ideas arise as a result of a person's special intention to imagine something specific, concrete.

Arbitrary imagination has 3 forms:

Recreative imagination (it manifests itself when a person needs to recreate a representation of an object that corresponds as fully as possible to its description. We encounter this type of imagination when we read a description of geographical places or historical events, as well as when we get acquainted with literary heroes). Recreative imagination is of great importance in mastering educational material. It is unthinkable to study geography without relying on recreated imagination.

- Creative imagination - the creation of a new, original image, idea. In this case, the word "new" has a dual meaning: a distinction is made between objectively and subjectively new.

- Objectively new - ideas that do not exist at the moment. This new does not repeat what already exists, it is original.

- Subjectively new - new for a given person. It can repeat what already exists, but the person does not know about it. He discovers it for himself as original, unique and considers it unknown to others.

Creative imagination proceeds as an analysis (decomposition) and synthesis (connection) of accumulated human knowledge. In this case, the elements, the "building blocks" from which the image is built, occupy a different position, a different place compared to what they occupied previously. A new image arises in a new combination of elements. A dream is the creation of an image of the desired future. Dreams express in a unique way what attracts a person, what he strives for. Secondly, a dream is a process of imagination that is not included in creative activity, i.e. does not immediately and directly produce an objective product in the form of a work of art, scientific discovery, technical invention, etc. The main feature of a dream is that it is aimed at future activity, i.e. a dream is imagination aimed at the desired future. Most often, a person makes plans for the future and in his dream determines the ways to achieve what he has planned. In this case, a dream is an active, arbitrary, conscious process.

Thus, a person creates new images based on previously perceived ones on the basis of imagination. Imagination occupies an intermediate position between perception, thinking and memory. It is one of the most mysterious mental phenomena, and it, i.e. imagination, is characteristic only of

man.

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